

COMMUNICATION CAPABILITIES IN VARIOUS RADIO FREQUENCY SPECTRUMS**Zakaryayev Z.***Military Institute named after Heydar Aliyev, Baku, Azerbaijan
ORCID ID 0009-0007-2764-9749***ABSTRACT**

This article is devoted to the topic of research of 5G millimeter wave radio channels. The capabilities of this network have been assessed. Problems associated with increasing load on networks, as well as communication capabilities in various radio frequency spectrums, are considered. The use of low-frequency spectrum for 5G networks is analyzed for optimal network coverage with minimal investment in the development of network infrastructure. The influence of interference on the propagation of radio waves in space and the influence of hydrometeors on the propagation of millimeter waves are assessed. Based on research, the rationality of using low frequencies for the effective penetration of radio waves into premises has been proven, as this is one of the important factors for IoT.

Keywords: millimeter waves, millimeter frequency, low frequencies, radio relay station.

The 5G network is a new stage in technology development, which is designed to expand the possibilities of internet access through radio access networks. MIMO- is a method of spatial signal encoding that allows you to increase the channel bandwidth, in which two or more antennas are used for data transmission and the same number of antennas for reception.

As mobile technology develops, the range of frequencies used to create mobile communication networks expands. The expansion of the list of frequency ranges is clearly visible when moving from one generation of communication to another [1]. The transition to fifth generation mobile networks is also no exception. When operating 5G networks, new frequency ranges will be used. The main requirements for such networks include requirements such as: high-speed data transmission, network coverage, servicing a huge number of connected devices, etc. In order to meet these requirements, a frequency resource is needed to launch 5G networks. To date, two such frequency ranges have been identified (Frequency Range, FR). FR1- 450-6000 MHz. This low frequency range is used to cover the network inside buildings, FR2-24250-52600 MHz is the high frequency range for crowded areas and places where there is high traffic.

They believe that such high speeds are unnecessary. But the coming global changes in the use of communications prove the opposite. Frequency ranges, station features and software will be needed not only by ordinary consumers, but also by the industrial complex, as well as urban infrastructure. 5G involves a completely new understanding of technology. Many industries will receive an impetus for development. Along with this, completely new services will appear, and interaction between devices will reach a new level [2].

An increase in the speed of information transmission is possible by expanding the frequency band used; also, the requirements for networks can only be implemented in the millimeter frequency range. This range is effective in areas with high electronic density.

The millimeter wave range has been well studied, but is not fully used. That is why research in this area is timely and represents a good prospect for the development of communications [3].

The 5G network architecture is constantly being developed to support the exchange of all kinds of data and provide various services using network virtualization (NFV - Network Function Virtualization) and software-defined networks (SDN - Software Defined Networking) technologies.

Such a network is designed to provide higher performance than previous generations of communication and at the same time should have a lower cost. Otherwise, it will be unattractive to investors.

5G networks are designed to serve devices with a wide variety of capabilities. Therefore, such a network must effectively manage network resources depending on application needs and quality of service requirements.

The network has limited frequency resources. This leads to the need to use radio access frequency bands from different ranges.

Performance for fifth generation networks is ensured through the introduction of new technologies, including radio access network, core network, and subscriber equipment.

The need for new radio interfaces to enable network performance has focused most of the innovation for 5G networks in the radio access network area. This will require the use of wide bandwidths of frequency channels, both downlink and uplink, with a contiguous spectrum width of 500 to 1000 MHz [4].

Taking into account the challenges of our time to the increasing demands to provide businesses and the population with high-quality communication services, the International Telecommunication Union decides to introduce 5G cellular communications, with a data transfer speed of at least 10 Gbit/s per millisecond. An increase in the speed of information transmission is possible by expanding the frequency band used; also, the requirements for networks can only be implemented in the millimeter frequency range. The millimeter wave range is a fairly well-studied topic, but millimeter waves are subject to strong attenuation.

Many modern scientists are engaged in research of the millimeter range: L.Frenzel, A.V.Chekanov, K.Rappaport and many others.

The assignment of radio frequency channels is carried out using various technologies of frequency-territorial planning with mandatory compatibility of different radio equipment. It is for this reason that the main direction for creating a new generation of communications is the development of frequency ranges above 5 GHz, which are still little used.

There are freer parts of the spectrum at ultra-high frequencies, but the millimeter wave range is the least developed.

This range is effective in areas with high electronic density.

In the world today, the millimeter wave is used in both satellite communications and terrestrial radio relay communications.

For example, for the needs of commercial communications, the frequency subranges 27-32 GHz, 36-38 GHz, 40-42.5 GHz are used. These frequencies are used for television broadcasting and telecommunications networks. Nevertheless, there are still free parts of the spectrum in the millimeter wave range, and they are a free niche for the creation and practical application of the new generation of 5G mobile communications.

Promising frequency bands for 5G:

1. The use of phased array antennas with high gain.
2. Use of diversity reception technologies.
3. Using MIMO technology, when several signals are sent and received simultaneously.
4. Application of noise-resistant coding when transmitting information.

The presence of free sections of the spectrum in the MW range creates a niche for the use of radio systems in this range when developing the new generation of 5G mobile communications. Compared to frequencies up to 3 GHz, millimeter wave frequencies are little used. The main reason is the strong attenuation of millimeter wave signals [5].

The main advantage of the millimeter wave is the ability to use a wide frequency band. Disadvantages - strong attenuation, the influence of precipitation on the level of the received signal, the presence of foreign bodies in the atmosphere, the influence of obstacles on the level of the received signal, the presence of zones of signal weakening in the millimeter frequency range by oxygen molecules and water vapor.

With proper accounting, it is possible to identify portions of the millimeter wave spectrum that are suitable for high-speed data transmission and broadband access.

The radio station is surrounded by many reflective objects with different reflective properties and different locations. The final signal at the receiving point is formed by many rays arriving in different ways. Signal attenuation also occurs when passing through the walls of buildings. Unlike low-frequency signals, which easily pass through various obstacles, millimeter-wave signals are greatly attenuated in solid materials [6]. Based on the above, we can identify the reasons for the weakening of signals in millimeter-wave radio channels:

- attenuation of radio waves as they propagate in the atmosphere;

- energy losses during propagation due to rain, hail, snow, etc;
- fading of millimeter wave signals due to multipath;
- change in the relative position of the antennas at the transmitting and receiving stations (for mobile subscribers);
- weakening of the signal when passing obstacles;
- attenuation of radio waves in free space.

In the millimeter range, significant absorption is caused by oxygen and water molecules. It is important that significant attenuation is observed around frequencies 60, 183, 320. At frequencies up to 110 GHz they do not exceed 1 dB/km. This means that intense absorption occurs at waves of 2.5 mm and 5 mm for oxygen, and at waves of 1.8 mm and 13.5 mm for water vapor. In almost the entire range, a linear relationship is observed between the absorption coefficient and rain intensity. The dependence of the absorption of millimeter-wave signals in rain on frequency in the work is approximated by an expression that, for showers with an intensity of 100 mm/h for the millimeter range 30-100 GHz, is in good agreement with the experimental results of other researchers.

Conclusions:

Currently, the existing global telecommunications infrastructure in the form of LTE is reaching its technical ceiling over time. This will be facilitated by the rapid development of various devices with Internet access. At the moment, mobile networks provide data transfer rates to the client side up to 1 Gbit/s. However, there are difficulties with a clear link to specific frequency bands and their aggregation. There are also issues with signal delays. All these issues should be resolved by the 5G standard. The millimeter wave range has been well studied, but is not fully used. That is why research in this area is timely and represents a good prospect for the development of communications.

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